

APPLICATION OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MODERN EDUCATIONAL PHYSICS

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Annotation: The article describes the role and importance of using innovative technologies in teaching repetition and generalization in physics education. Also, the article is devoted to the issues of increasing the effectiveness of education by conducting classes with the introduction of modern pedagogical technologies.

Key words: repetition, generalization, mastery levels, mass, force, weight, Newton's laws.

Introduction. By increasing the efficiency of the educational process, the ground is created for the further development and strengthening of the future development. Every teacher knows that the lesson is the main form of the learning process. Therefore, the teacher, first of all, thinks about passing the lesson and improving the lesson. Today, while reforms are being carried out in the field of education in our country, it is necessary to improve the quality of teaching mathematics and natural sciences, to establish the level of mastery of students on the basis of pedagogical technologies by clearly defining educational, educational, developmental and interest goals in modern classes, and in the future it is necessary to educate young people with active, creative, innovative ideas. It is known that the definition of content in modern physics classes is organized and carried out on the basis of state educational standards, educational programs, textbooks and training manuals, and information from Internet sources. In order for the content of physics to correspond to the level of scientific and technical development, advanced production technologies, and society's culture, a physics teacher should choose specific materials from various sources, familiarize himself with the problems of the field, and organize their study. without breaking the logic of the subject. In doing so, he should compare the material he identified with both the program and the textbook.

Materials and methods. The most important key points to be studied and mastered and the material presented in the form of information are identified. The essence of physical concepts, quantities, mathematical expressions and experiments is determined depending on their complexity. In modern repetition and generalization lessons of the basics of physics, the material should be selected in such a way that the knowledge is not ready in the form of a summary, but allows students to independently find the correct answers to the questions. To create such conditions, it is necessary to be able to use and apply innovative pedagogical technologies, to take into account the nature of science. It is known that innovation (innovation) is the introduction of innovations. A.I. Prigogine understands innovation as purposeful changes that introduce new, relatively stable elements to a certain social unit - organization, population, society, group, this is innovative activity. A new direction of educational development - the term "innovative pedagogy" and its specific studies appeared in Western Europe and the USA in the 60s of the 20th century [1]. Taking into account that students studying physics and mathematics will become scientists or engineers in the future, it is not enough to organize practical training in this way. In addition to the traditional problems in the classroom, students should also present quality and assessment problems in order to

have a thorough knowledge of physics. Quality issues require a proper understanding of the underlying process and the understanding and description of process interrelationships based on physical laws. [2]

Discussion. Physics always goes from theory to practice. Therefore, it is possible to conduct the lesson in the form of a laboratory without directly explaining the topic, and then bring to the attention of the students the question of its content and the basis on which it is based. Or by randomly placing the tools on the lab table, students are asked to choose the tools they need for the job. This method can be used in small groups using interactive methods.

Therefore, there are some problems in the use of innovative pedagogical technologies in the organization and conduct of repetition and generalization lessons in physics in general secondary schools. Including:

- Sufficient information about physical quantities, concepts, mathematical expressions, formulas, units, measuring instruments, which need to be systematized, defined and revived by repetition and generalization in physics classes, should be taught based on new methods. should be remembered for a long time and be sufficient for use in subsequent sections of physics;
- the need to use new analytical methods that serve to distinguish similar concepts (body weight, gravity, body mass);
- it is necessary to restore certain rules and apply them to the desired result;
- Taking into account that the methods used in the repetition and generalization lessons are organized based on the topics covered, the lesson should not be boring, but requires high learning, independent research, critical thinking, and the development of creative activity in students. In this case, the basic concepts taught in the "Department of Dynamics" in our example, body mass, body weight, interaction, force, gravity, relativity of motion, etc., are expanded and deepened in all other departments of physics.

Conclusion. In general, the purpose of using modern technologies is to teach students to think logically in class, to express their opinions freely, to self-evaluate, to work individually and in groups. passing, teaching students to express their opinions, to express their opinion freely, to correct their opinion. that is, not teaching the child, but guiding students in their work aimed at achieving continuous improvement of the quality of knowledge and pedagogical skills, as well as methods selection and effective application, as correct selection of methods and effective application in practice¹. Thus, the application and correct organization of pedagogical technologies in the generalization and reinforcement lessons of physics, knowledge of the basic laws of nature on a scientific basis, and improvement of students' mastery skills. It provides creative and logical thinking at a wider level, provides comparative study of natural phenomena, teaches systematization of acquired knowledge, serves to educate creative and active young people in the future.

References:

1. Mavlyanov A et al. The technology of conducting lessons based on the principles of pedagogical technology "VORIS-Nashriyot" - T.: 2010. 112 b
2. Tursunmetov Q.A., Uzokov A.A., Boriboev I. Collection of problems from physics. Curriculum for academic lyceums and vocational colleges.
4th edition. Teacher, 2005
3. Ishmuhamedov R.J., Abdukadirov A.A., Pardaev A.Kh. Innovative technologies in education. - T.: "Talent", 2008.
4. Yoldoshev J.G., Usmanov S.A. Introduction of modern pedagogical technologies. - T.: "Science and Technology", 2008. - p. 124.
5. Izbosarov V.F., Kamolov I.R. Mechanics. - T.: "LEADER PRESS", 2009
6. Azizkhojaeva N.N. Pedagogical technologies and pedagogical skills. - T.: Literary Fund of the Writers' Association of Uzbekistan, 2006. - p. 52.